

results of columns 2-4 and included in column 6 of the Table 1. The g-atom ratio $(Ca+Ba+Zn)/P$, in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of columns 2-5 and given in column B of the Table. The fact that the observed value of molar g-atom ratios of Ca/P , Ba/P , Zn/P for the end members and $(Ca+Ba+Zn)/P$, were found to be equal to 1.645 (theoretical 1.67) is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solution¹⁰. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by the X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal crystals, belonging to hexagonal bipyramidal class-6/m (space group $P6_3/m$)^{11,12}. Lattice parameter showed unit cell dilation and contraction consequent upon the introduction of bigger ion Ba^{II} (1.35 Å) and smaller ion Zn^{II} (0.74 Å), respectively in place of Ca^{II} ion (0.99 Å) in the apatite lattice. Such dilation and contraction with the proportion of $Ca-Ba-Zn$ HA was evident that the unit cell volume of the sample calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constant increased with the proportion of barium content and decreased with the proportion of zinc content in $Ca-Ba-Zn$ HA.

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N_1 -Substituted-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles and N_1 -Substituted-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones and Related Compounds as Possible Fungicides

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PYRAZOLE derivatives have been associated with antifungal¹, antibacterial² and antimicrobial³ activities. Irikura⁴ reported that 3,5-dimethylpyrazoles have antidiabetic property. Substituted pyrazolones have been known as antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶, antimicrobial⁷ and antiinflammatory⁸ agents. We have, therefore, synthesised the title compounds which might show enhanced biological activity due to the presence of an additional aryloxy-acetyl/carbonyl moiety.

N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles (1) were prepared by refluxing aroyl/aryloxyacetylhydrazine with acetylacetone. N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (2) have been obtained by the reaction of aroyl/aryloxyacetylhydrazine and ethyl acetoacetate. The condensation of 2 with an aryl aldehyde in the presence of fused sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid yielded corresponding monoarylidene derivatives (3). 3 decolourise bromine water and show a broad peak at $\sim 1695\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of ring ketone.

The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, ir and nmr spectra.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded in $CDCl_3$ solution. The compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines: These were prepared by the method of Conti⁹.

N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles¹⁰ (1): A methanolic solution (20 ml) of aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01 M) and acetylacetone (0.01 M) was refluxed gently for 3 h. On evaporation, the solid obtained was washed and recrystallised with aqueous ethanol: (1) $R=2,6-(CH_3)_2-C_6H_3-OCH_3$, (87%), m.p. 68° ; ν_{max} 1600 (CO.N), 1540 (C=N), 1050 (=C-O-C-) and 745 cm^{-1}

(*o*-disubst. -C₆H₆); (2) R=3,5-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, (89%), m.p. 86°; (3) R=2-(CH₃)₂CH-5-CH₃-C₆H₃-OCH₃, (55%), m.p. 61°; (4) R=2-Cl.C₆H₄, (73%), m.p. 58°; ν_{max} 1680 (CO.N), 1590 (C=N), 760 (1,2,3-trisubst. -C₆H₃) and 740 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ 1.5 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.6 (1H, s, vinyl) and 7.4 (4H, m, Ar).

N₁-Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones¹¹
 (2): A solution of aroyl/aryloxyacetylhydrazine (0.01 M) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 M) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed gently for 3 h. On evaporation, the solid obtained was washed and recrystallised with aqueous ethanol: (6) R=2,4-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, (96%), m.p.¹⁴ 84°; (7) R=4-Cl-3-CH₃-OCH₃, (96%), m.p.¹⁴ 106°; (8) R=3,5-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃.OCH₃, (95%), m.p. 85°; ν_{max} 1700 (ring C=O), 1640 (CO.N), 1500 (C=N) and 1040 cm⁻¹ (=C-O-C); δ 1.2-1.8 (9H, m, CH₃), 2.6-2.8 (4H, b, CO.CH₃) and 17.6 (3H, m, Ar); (9) R=2-Cl.C₆H₄, (96%), m.p. 65°; ν_{max} 1725 (ring C=O), 1600 (CO.N), 1490 (C=N) and 750 (*o*-disubst. -C₆H₆); (10) 2-CH₃-C₆H₄, (76%), m.p. 87°; and (11) R=3-CH₃.C₆H₄, (82%), m.p. 75°.

N₁-Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-4-arylidene-2-pyrazoline-5-ones (3): N₁-Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01 M) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5 ml). To it fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) and an aryl aldehyde (0.01 M) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled and poured into cold water. The solid separating out was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol: (12) R=2,4-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=H, (66%), m.p. 119°; ν_{max} 3100 (CH=C), 1675 (ring C=O), 1600 (CO-N), 1520 (C=N) and 1020 cm⁻¹ (=C-O-C); (13) R=4-Cl-3-CH₃.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=H, (81%), m.p. 136°; (14) R=3,5-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=H, (71%), m.p. 80°; (15) R=2-Cl.C₆H₄, R'=H, (61%), m.p. 132°; (16) R=3-CH₃.C₆H₄, R'=H, (52%), m.p. 128°; (17) R=2-CH₃.C₆H₄, R'=H, (55%), m.p. 115°; (18) R=2,4-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=2-Cl, (67%), m.p. 102°; (19) R=4-Cl-3-CH₃.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=2-Cl, (64%), m.p. 104°; (20) 3,5-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=2-Cl, (81%), m.p. 94°; (21) 2-Cl.C₆H₄, R'=4-Cl, (65%), m.p. 124°; (22) 3-CH₃.C₆H₄, R'=4-Cl, (79%), m.p. 110°; (23) R=2-CH₃.C₆H₄, R'=2-Cl, (62%), m.p. 182°; ν_{max} 3050 (CH=C), 1695 (ring C=O), 1640 (CO.N), 1500 (CN), 755 (*o*-disubst. -C₆H₆) and 730 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ 1.2 (6H, m, CH₃), 4.6 (1H, s, vinyl) and 7.7 (1H, s, Ar); (24) R=2,4-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=4-OH, (58%), m.p. 182°; (25) R=4-Cl-3-CH₃.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=4-OH, (66%), m.p. 165°; ν_{max} 3200 (CH=C), 1690 (ring C=O), 1600 (CO.N), 1490 (C=N), 1060 (=C-O-C), 810 (*p*-disubst. -C₆H₆) and 750 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); (26) R=3,5-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃-OCH₃, R'=4-OH, (60%), m.p. 192°; (27) R=2-Cl.C₆H₄, R'=4-OH, (63%), m.p. 201°; (28) R=3-CH₃.C₆H₄, R'=4-OH, (59%), m.p. 160° d; and (29) R=2-CH₃.C₆H₄, R'=4-OH, (70%), m.p. 231°.

Fungicidal screening: The compounds were screened for antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique^{12,13} at three different concentrations, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. Two commercial fungicides Memcge and Blitox 50 WP have also been tested under similar conditions to compare the result. The number of replications in each case was three.

Results and Discussion

The compounds screened display moderate to good antifungal activity against both the fungi. The pyrazole 1 (3) and monoarylidene-pyrazolones 3 (19 and 20) inhibit > 44% the growth of both the test organisms even at 10 ppm concentration, and possess fungitoxicity of the order of Memcge and Blitox 50 WP at 1000 ppm concentration. The pyrazolones (2) are less fungitoxic than their corresponding pyrazoles (1) against *A. niger* but show more or similar activity against *H. oryzae*.

TABLE I—FUNGICIDAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Average percentage inhibition after 96 h					
	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>H. oryzae</i>		
	Concn. (ppm)			Concn. (ppm)		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
1	84.0	58.3	40.6	82.5	56.6	41.0
2	84.5	57.5	40.2	84.3	59.3	42.1
3	96.2	65.4	52.0	94.5	68.0	54.8
4	78.6	52.3	33.0	78.2	51.4	32.2
8	77.0	56.2	35.8	82.5	58.4	42.2
9	76.3	49.6	30.3	80.1	47.6	33.0
10	68.3	45.0	24.5	73.0	43.4	30.3
11	55.7	38.6	22.8	73.4	51.0	30.0
12	75.4	57.4	35.3	82.0	61.4	36.8
13	82.6	58.0	39.0	83.5	62.6	39.3
14	78.2	56.8	36.8	85.6	58.5	42.9
15	78.0	56.2	35.8	82.4	60.5	36.9
18	84.6	57.4	41.8	87.5	62.4	45.3
19	94.7	62.2	46.7	95.0	65.3	48.4
20	92.5	58.7	43.3	93.3	59.0	44.0
22	80.2	52.5	32.6	80.7	48.4	35.8
23	76.6	48.7	31.0	82.4	57.3	36.2
24	77.8	54.5	36.5	84.0	58.6	37.8
27	72.0	54.0	35.9	81.5	52.4	35.7
28	66.7	42.6	26.8	74.4	48.5	31.0
29	68.4	45.3	27.7	69.7	46.6	29.6
Memcge	94.2	87.4	83.8	91.0	83.2	75.6
Blitox						
50 WP	90.4	78.2	73.4	98.5	65.6	80.0

In general, monoarylidene-pyrazolones (3) are relatively more potent than the corresponding pyrazolones (2). Further, the substituents at 4-position of monoarylidene-pyrazolones (3) confer fungicidal activity in the order, *o*-chlorobenzylideno > *p*-hydroxybenzylideno > benzylideno.

Introduction of an aryloxyacetyl group at N₁-position invariably increases the fungitoxicity of the compound.

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**Polysaccharide from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*
Linn. Seeds-isolation, Purification and
Preliminary Analysis of Polysaccharide**

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NYCTANTHES *arbor-tristis* Linn. (Fam. :
Oleaceae ; Hindi : *Harsingar*, *Parajita*) is a large
shrub, 15-25 feet high and is widely cultivated as a
garden plant throughout India. The seeds are known
for their use in Ayurvedic system of medicine for
throat, leprosy, eye diseases, skin infections, intesti-
nal worm infection etc. The systematic chemical
investigation of the seed polysaccharide has not been
reported so far. The present communication
reports the isolation of a polysaccharide in the pure
form, and the nature of the constituent sugars.

Experimental

Isolation : The seeds (200 g) were washed with
water to remove completely the outer covering.
Subsequently the seeds were crushed in a hand
grinder into a greyish white powder. The powder
(100 g) was soaked in water (900 ml) overnight and

stirred for 48 h. The resulting viscous solution was
squeezed through muslin cloth and centrifuged at
25000 r.p.m. in Sharple's super centrifuge to remove
finely suspended matter. The centrifugate was
treated with ethanol (2 dm³) to precipitate the poly-
saccharide in the form of light brown coarse
powder. It was filtered through sintered funnel
(G-3) under suction and the residual polysaccharide
dried *in vacuo* at 60° after washing with acetone and
ether. The white amorphous powder of the poly-
saccharide (8.2 g) had sulphated ash 1.982%, as
determined by sulphated ash method¹; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 32^\circ$
(H₂O).

Purification : The above polysaccharide (2 g)
was dissolved in water (200 ml) with constant
mechanical stirring for 12 h and the solution treated
with ethanol in stages. First the concentration of
ethanol was made upto 20% in the solution. It pre-
cipitated out some impurities which was allowed to
settle overnight and then centrifuged. The centri-
fugate was further treated with ethanol to have its
concentration to 30% in the solution to precipitate
higher molecular weight polysaccharide and
removed by centrifugation. Ethanol concentration
in the supernatant liquor was increased to 40% and
then to 60%, when rest of the polysaccharides pre-
cipitated out. The polysaccharide obtained by 40%
and 60% ethanol concentration were triturated with
absolute ethanol, acetone and ether and dried over
calcium chloride *in vacuo* at 60° (1.5240 g), sulphated
ash 0.632%; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 28.4^\circ$ (H₂O) for 40%, and $[\alpha]_D^{25} +$
 29.2° (H₂O) for 60%, respectively. This indicated
that the two polysaccharides were probably identical
and this was corroborated by their identical infrared
spectra.

The purified polysaccharide was in the form of
white amorphous powder; it did not reduce
Fehling's solution. Nitrogen, sulphur, halogens,
acetyl group², uronic acid³, methoxyl group⁴,
pentosans⁵, pentoses⁶ and furfural⁶ were absent in
it and it formed a highly viscous solution in water.

Nature of sugars : The purified polysaccharide
(2 g) was kept with sulphuric acid⁸ (72%, 8 ml) over-
night at room temperature. The slurry was cooled
in a freezing mixture and diluted with water (112 ml)
to make up a normal solution with respect to
sulphuric acid. The solution was heated for 12 h at
100° in boiling water-bath, when the hydrolysis
which was followed iodometrically⁷, was found to be
completed.

The hydrolysate was neutralised with barium
carbonate and filtered. The resulting solution, was
passed through Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺) and Amberlite
IR-45 (OH⁻) ion-exchange resins and concentrated
to a thin syrup. P.c. by descending method^{9,10} using
n-butanol-ethanol-water mixture (4:1:5, upper
phase)¹⁰ and *p*-anisidine phosphate¹¹ as a spray
reagent, revealed the presence of glucose and
mannose.

Resolution of sugars by column chromatography :
A column of Whatman standard chromatographic

* A/35, Alok Nagar, Jaipur House, Agra-282 002.